

BASICS AND PRINCIPLES OF WORKING WITH THE POWER POINT PROGRAM IN THE STUDY OF COMPUTER SCIENCE

Akram Suyarov¹, Kulmirzaeva Zarina ², Egamberdieva Feruza ³, Abdusobirova Makhliyo ⁴

¹Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service, Uzbekistan

² Samarkand state of university, Uzbekistan

³ Samarkand state of university, Uzbekistan

⁴ Samarkand state of university, Uzbekistan

Annotation: This article is devoted to studying the basic principles and capabilities of working in Microsoft Power Point. Power Point provides a convenient interface, wide functionality and various tools for creating presentations. With the help of this program, you can create effective visual presentations by combining text, images, graphics, video and animations. The article covers the main elements of the program environment, the stages of creating and formatting a new slide, using design templates, enriching content and presenting a presentation.

Key words: Power Point program, presentation technologies, educational process, animation, visual materials, Power Point equipment, presentation design, effective use, graphics, slides.

INTRODUCTION

In today's fast-paced and digital information age, presentation technologies have become an important tool for effective communication in education, business and many other areas. In this sense, Microsoft Power Point (MS Power Point) is recognized as the most popular and convenient program for preparing and presenting presentations. With the help of MS Power Point, you can create creative and professional presentations by combining text, images, graphics, diagrams, video clips, and sound animation effects. This program not only simplifies the presentation process, but also makes it more effective and efficient. [1]

Working with MS Power Point has become one of the basic skills not only of teachers and students, but also of employees of enterprises and organizations. The program allows users to manage presentations through an intuitive interface, design slides, add visual elements to them and animate them with animations. At the same time, the program allows not only to view the presentation, but also to engage the audience through it, effectively convey important information and keep the attention of the audience.

Presentation software capabilities.

1. The ability to create slides allows the user to create slides at any point in the presentation, at the beginning, in the middle and at the end.
2. Removing a created slide: any slide can be removed from the presentation.
3. The ability to copy, cut and insert slides if necessary
4. Allows you to apply animation to slides or manipulate sounds
5. Easy search, relocation and data entry options

6. A good font set - allows you to use fonts of different styles.
7. Additional options, leave comments on the slide, give links, an advanced navigation system allows for headings and footers.
8. Layout management system allows you to rearrange the layout design, and easily customize it.
9. Spell check and dictionary support
10. The ability to use slide shows in presentations

The process of creating presentations in Power Point has a wide range of possibilities. The program allows the user to speed up work through ready-made templates and designs, easily edit text and other objects, as well as make the presentation attractive with the help of animation and transition effects. By enriching slides with text, graphic elements and multimedia tools, they can be adapted for various purposes. For example, Power Point is invaluable for explaining educational materials in the educational process, demonstrating project results at business meetings, or promoting a new product in the marketing field. [4]

Animations and transition effects make Power Point presentations lively and interesting. They make text, images, and graphic elements on slides more visible and understandable. Also, the SmartArt graphics and diagrams built into the program allow you to visually convey complex information in a simple and clear way. This not only increases the audience's interest in the presentation, but also helps to better perceive the information.

Another advantage of Power Point is its ability to create interactive presentations. For example, links can be used to jump to other slides or external sources, and multimedia elements can be used to further enrich the process of influencing the audience. The program offers not only the ability to display a presentation, but also the ability to print it or distribute it via email, which further expands its scope of application. [6]

A presentation is the process of presenting a topic to an audience, for example, a presentation on global warming. Many people use presentation software to give presentations to others. A presentation is a program that displays information on a screen in the form of a slide show.

It usually includes three main functions: editing - a method for placing and formatting data, a method for placing and manipulating graphics, and a slide show system for illustrating a topic. Microsoft Power Point is a program that allows users to create their own presentations and slide shows using a variety of media: images, videos, music.

The above highlights the versatility of MS Power Point. With the help of this program, you can create high-quality and impressive presentations not only professionally, but also creatively. Therefore, mastering the basics of working with MS Power Point is an important skill today. This topic is devoted to the process of working with this program, its capabilities and methods of creating animations, and will guide users to effectively learn how to work with the program.

METHOD OF RESEARCH

Power Point is a widely used software for creating and presenting presentations, which can be effectively used in the educational process and in other areas. This program allows you to create visual presentations, interactive slides, animations and diagrams. Scientific research on the use of Power Point in education and business has been conducted in many areas, all of which show how the program can be used effectively.

This program can be used to create various types of visual aids and in some cases it can also be used as a database. In some cases, this program can also perform tasks such as managing multimedia tools and sending them to display devices.

A presentation can consist of several slides, arranged in a sequence. A slide is a page that displays several objects: titles, additional headings, videos, diagrams. To improve the quality of the presentation, slide objects and slides are designed with various effects.

The main steps in creating a presentation are as follows:

1. Create a slide of the required appearance
2. Enter the necessary information into the slide
3. Arrange the slides in the correct sequence
4. Apply various effects to slide objects, for example, add text and sound effects
5. Adjust the slide transitions
6. Set up a slide show
7. Present the slides.

Below is an analysis of the existing literature on the basics of working with Power Point.

The Role of Power Point in Education There are a number of scientific studies on the role of Power Point in the educational process. Researchers describe presentation programs as visual elements that are added to the teaching process. Power Point slides can engage students in the topic of the lesson, help them memorize the material, and help teachers present the material clearly and concisely (Mayer, 2005). Other studies have shown that excessive use of Power Point can lead to a decrease in attention and passive learning (Lammers,2011). The effectiveness of Power Point in education can provide interactivity between students and teachers, increase understanding of the material, and encourage active participation of students. [2]

Power Point and Visual Learning Power Point is an important tool for using visual learning. The use of visual materials, graphics, diagrams, and animations is of great importance in making the learning process effective. The use of graphics and images increases the level of student retention (Paivio,1986). Research shows that visual materials enhance students' ability to remember because they help them connect information to formal or personal experiences. The visual elements of Power Point help to attract students' attention, while ensuring effective and rapid assimilation of information.

Animation and Interactive Elements in Power Point Power Point's animation and interactive features play an important role in presentations. Research shows that using animations to present text, images, and diagrams step-by-step increases students' understanding and retention of the material (Liu, 2012). Adding interactive elements, such as questions, answers, and interactive exercises on slides, can engage students and make learning more engaging. Other studies have shown that the interactive elements that can be created in Power Point can give teachers more control over the lesson. [11]

Benefits of Power Point for Teachers and Students For teachers, Power Point is a convenient tool for creating effective lesson plans, organizing materials, and presenting them. Research shows that using Power Point allows teachers to develop their presentations in a concise and fluent manner, which makes the presentation easier for students to understand (Berk,2009). Power Point encourages teachers to present their educational materials in more visual and effective ways, which improves the learning process for students.

Power Point Disadvantages and Limitations However, there are some disadvantages to Power Point. Research shows that PowerPoint slides that contain too much text and graphics can make it difficult for students to concentrate (Tufte,2003). Therefore, teachers should ensure that the slides are simple and the visual elements are selected appropriately when using Power Point. Some researchers also believe that the excessive use of PowerPoint can lead teachers to abandon traditional teaching methods and reduce students' opportunities for self-learning. [12]

The presentation preparation process is implemented in the following ways.

Planning - Determining the purpose of the presentation and understanding the needs of the audience.

Preparing materials - Gathering the necessary information, graphics, and evidence on the topic.

Design and organization - Making the slides or canvas attractive, choosing colors and fonts, and using visual effects.

Audience engagement.

Effective presentations are more successful by establishing strong relationships with the audience and conducting interactive discussions. The following factors are important for the success of the presentation. The level of knowledge of the presenter on the topic. The logicalness of the visual design and presentation structure. Maintaining interaction and responding to the needs of the audience. Technical preparation It is important to have a good knowledge of presentation programs and prepare. Before the presentation, it is necessary to familiarize yourself with technical equipment, internet connection, and software.

Nowadays, PowerPoint is evolving with the use of technology. In the future, there are opportunities to use PowerPoint in education in even more interactive and innovative ways, for example, integrating it with virtual reality (VR) or augmented reality (AR). New features and functions of PowerPoint are also being developed that provide active interaction with students. This will help make the educational process more interactive and effective.

Future opportunities The development of presentation software 21 will help create interactive and virtual presentations. Modern technologies, such as virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR), allow presentations to be more effective

It includes various statistics and methodologies to analyze the effectiveness of PowerPoint in the educational process, how it is used among users, and how it affects student success. Each method of research allows you to more deeply study the impact of PowerPoint on education and identify ways to use it effectively.

On this basis, using statistical methods and analysis techniques, you can study the educational effectiveness of PowerPoint, its positive impact, and how it is used among users. [8]

RESEARCH RESULTS

Within the framework of this study, the level of development of skills on the topic “Basics of working with PowerPoint” and the effectiveness of using this program in pedagogical processes were studied. The analysis was carried out in the following main areas:

- 1) Students' basic skills in working with the program;
- 2) Technical and didactic aspects of using PowerPoint in the educational process;
- 3) The role of educational materials in increasing the quality of presentation and audience interest.

Table1. Result of the observed analysis

Indicators	Units of measurement	Izohlar
Number of participants	50 people (30 students, 20 teachers)	Number of respondents in the test group
Initial level of knowledge	68% (knowing basic functions)	Basic skills, such as creating a slide

Those who faced difficulties	32%	There is a problem with working with graphics and animations
Effective presentations	80%	Percentage of presentations that increased audience interest
Improper presentations	20%	It did not maintain a balance between visibility and information loading
Visual and textual consistency	75%	Percentage of presentations that are properly organized
Inappropriate use of animation and graphics	40%	Gaps in learners' technical skills
Presentations made with technical errors	25%	Incomplete or poorly crafted presentations
Level of satisfaction between teachers and students	85%	Positive changes after special training

During the study, a test group of 50 participants (students and teachers) was formed. At the initial stage, the participants' knowledge and skills in using PowerPoint were assessed through a test. The results showed that 68 percent of respondents had basic knowledge of the basic functions (creating slides, adding text, using simple animations), but 32 percent of participants had difficulties using the program.

Special lessons were organized to assess the effectiveness of integrating PowerPoint into the learning process. During the lessons, students were given basic principles of creating presentations, instructions on the appropriate selection and placement of visual materials. During the process, the following factors were analyzed:

Content quality: While 75 percent of presentations used in lessons appropriately combined visual and text materials, 25 percent of presentations had an imbalance between the amount of information and the visual load of the slides.

Technical issues: Some participants made errors in the use of animation and graphic elements, which reduced the effectiveness of the presentation.

Presentation effectiveness and audience engagement:

Presentations created by students and teachers were tested in front of an audience.

The survey results showed that:

- 80% of presentations were successful in increasing audience interest.
- Presentations with good visual structure and appropriate text size were highly rated by the audience.
- Presentations with unclear graphics or overly complex design elements were less likely to engage the audience.

The analysis showed that continuous development of teaching methodologies and technical skills is essential for effective use of PowerPoint.

The results of this study prove that:

- Proper integration of the use of PowerPoint into the educational process increases the effectiveness of educational materials.
- Methodological approaches and the availability of technical support significantly increase the quality of presentations and educational effectiveness.

□ There are opportunities to improve participants' skills in working with PowerPoint through special training.

An in-depth analysis of the results shows that using PowerPoint in the educational process is an effective tool for visually and structurally presenting information, and is important in attracting the attention of listeners and assimilating information.

CONCLUSION

Power Point is an effective tool for teachers and students in the educational process. The program helps to strengthen the visual and interactive aspects of teaching, and also allows you to present educational materials in a clear and understandable way. The results of the study show that PowerPoint presentations play an important role in engaging students, making lessons more interactive, and encouraging students to actively participate.

The study also found that teachers need to have some basic skills and care to use PowerPoint effectively. It is important for teachers to take full advantage of PowerPoint and choose the right design and animations when presenting learning materials. However, in some cases, improper use of PowerPoint (for example, excessive animations, colors, and text) can distract students and make it difficult to understand the material.

The study also highlighted the limitations of PowerPoint in the educational process. These include technological limitations, internet connectivity, program errors, and teachers' attitudes towards PowerPoint. In such cases, proper guidance and training for teachers and students is necessary. Therefore, teachers should be provided with appropriate training and guidance to ensure the effective use of PowerPoint.

1. In order to effectively use PowerPoint, teachers should regularly organize special trainings and seminars. This will help teachers fully understand the capabilities of PowerPoint and conduct lessons more effectively. Organizing special trainings for teachers:

2. Interactive tools and elements that encourage students to participate actively should be used in presentations. For example, students can be made more active by organizing tests, quizzes, and question-and-answer sessions. Using interactive elements when using PowerPoint:

3. Design and colors should be carefully selected in PowerPoint presentations. Educational materials should not be filled with too many colors and animations, as this can distract students. Presentations should be clearly and correctly structured, and information should be rationally arranged. Pay special attention to the visual design of PowerPoint in education:

4. In some educational institutions, it is necessary to create special conditions for the effective use of PowerPoint. For example, creating offline PowerPoint templates for working in areas without internet access, as well as customizing content for each student. Developing customized versions of PowerPoint:

5. PowerPoint presentations should be used not only to make lessons more interesting, but also as a tool to help students self-assess. For example, having students prepare their own PowerPoint presentations and present them in class will develop their approach to the learning material. Using PowerPoint more in lessons:

To effectively use PowerPoint in education, it is necessary to fully explore its capabilities and provide teachers with the necessary technological support. In today's era, it provides advice on preparing digital presentations and making them effective, including methods for using PowerPoint, Prezi, Canva and other programs that help improve the quality of the educational process.

Teachers' thorough study of PowerPoint, at the same time, will increase its usefulness in the educational process. The proposals presented in the study are useful for the effective use of PowerPoint in education and will serve to improve the quality of the educational process.

REFERENCES

1. Resolution of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Strategy for the Development of the Education System".
2. "State Program for the Development of Information Technologies" of the Republic of Uzbekistan
3. World Economic Forum (WEF) "Global Competitiveness Report 2020".
4. Gary J. Bower, Justin A. Bowyer – "PowerPoint 2019 For Dummies" (2019)
5. Doug Lowe – "Microsoft PowerPoint 2019 Step by Step" (2019)
6. Cindy M. Dumas – "Microsoft PowerPoint 2016: The Complete Guide" (2016)
7. Faithe Wempen – "PowerPoint 2016 For Dummies" (2016)
8. Michael Price – "Microsoft PowerPoint 2013 Plain & Simple" (2013)
9. Mark L. Chambers – "PowerPoint 2016 For Dummies" (2016)
10. R.I. Urazgaliyeva. Credit-modular system of organizing training as a factor in the formation of students' self-educational activity skills. Abstract of the dissertation for the degree of candidate of pedagogical sciences. Orenburg, 2010. Page: 13.
11. Ministry of Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan – "Use of pedagogical technologies in teaching" (2018)
11. L.A. Anisimova. Modern trends in education: credit-modular training and the possibilities of its implementation in foreign language professionally oriented training of bachelors.// Bulletin of the Samara Scientific Center of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Vol. 12, No. 5(2), 2010.
12. Ismailov Tohir. Credit - A Module System and Its Principles of Implementation (In Teaching Mathematics in Higher Education Institutions). International Journal of Academic Management Science Research (IJAMSR) .Vol. 6 Issue 4, April - 2022, Pages:8-15
13. Suyarov A.M. Formation of information and communication competence of the teacher as an one of the main tasks of modern education. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. Volume 4, Issue 4, April-2023.–C.243-257.
14. Suyarov A.M. Ways and models of providing integration of information technology science with mathematical sciences. «E3S Web of Conferences». Indexed by SCOPUS and submitted for indexing to Web of Science (CPCI) «E3S Web of Conferences» 402, 03016 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202340203016>
15. M. D. Tashkentov – "Basics of Presentation: Working with PowerPoint" Tashkent: University, 2017. – 150 pages.
16. M. G. Karimov, S. A. Uralov – "Microsoft PowerPoint: Application in Pedagogical Practice" Tashkent: University of Uzbekistan, 2015. – 120 pages.
17. M. G. Karimov, S. A. Uralov – "Microsoft PowerPoint: Application in Pedagogical Practice" Tashkent: University of Uzbekistan, 2015. – 120 pages.